

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) op-8-36-1

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: op-8-36-1

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0025 A Wavelength=1.54184

Cell: a=10.9358(3) b=11.9819(4) c=13.2216(3)
 alpha=105.448(2) beta=94.284(2) gamma=108.634(3)
Temperature: 140 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1557.91(9)	1557.91(8)
Space group	P -1	P -1
Hall group	-P 1	-P 1
Moiety formula	C30 H34 B2 Co N6 O6 [+ solvent]	C30 H34 B2 Co N6 O6, 0.5[C H2 CL2]
Sum formula	C30 H34 B2 Co N6 O6 [+ solvent]	C30 H34 B2 Co N6 O6
Mr	655.18	655.18
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.397	1.397
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	4.758	4.758
F000	682.0	682.0
F000'	679.26	
h,k,lmax	13,15,16	13,14,16
Nref	6504	6399
Tmin,Tmax	0.796,0.909	0.303,1.000
Tmin'	0.038	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.303 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = GAUSSIAN

Data completeness= 0.984 Theta(max)= 75.928

R(reflections)= 0.0341(5985) wR2(reflections)= 0.0867(6399)

S = 1.043 Npar= 506

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

PLAT911_ALERT_3_C Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600 8 Report

Alert level G

FORMU01_ALERT_1_G There is a discrepancy between the atom counts in the
_chemical_formula_sum and _chemical_formula_moiety. This is
usually due to the moiety formula being in the wrong format.
Atom count from _chemical_formula_sum: C30 H34 B2 Co1 N6 O6
Atom count from _chemical_formula_moiety:C30.5 H35 B2 Cl1 Co1 N6 O6

PLAT002_ALERT_2_G Number of Distance or Angle Restraints on AtSite 21 Note
PLAT003_ALERT_2_G Number of Uiso or Uij Restrained non-H Atoms ... 24 Report
PLAT063_ALERT_4_G Crystal Size Possibly too Large for Beam Size .. 0.69 mm
PLAT176_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SADI Records 4 Report
PLAT178_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SIMU Records 1 Report
PLAT232_ALERT_2_G Hirshfeld Test Diff (M-X) Col --N4 . 5.9 s.u.
PLAT232_ALERT_2_G Hirshfeld Test Diff (M-X) Col --N5 . 5.0 s.u.
PLAT301_ALERT_3_G Main Residue Disorder(Resd 1) 27% Note
PLAT605_ALERT_4_G Largest Solvent Accessible VOID in the Structure 110 A**3
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels 20 Note
PLAT811_ALERT_5_G No ADDSYM Analysis: Too Many Excluded Atoms ! Info
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G Number of Least-Squares Restraints 334 Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 91 Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G Number of OMIT Records in Embedded .res File ... 1 Note
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity 2.5 Low
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 11 Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
1 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
17 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

1 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
6 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
4 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
6 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 18/09/2020; check.def file version of 20/08/2020

